

Prevalence Of Pathogens in Intensive Care Unit Patients with Lower Respiratory Tract Infections: Culture With/Without Polymerase Chain Reaction?

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Introduction

The lower respiratory tract infections (LRTI) are a leading cause of hospitalization and death globally [1]. The early initiation of appropriate antibiotics in patients with LRTI is crucial as postponing effective antibiotic administration can adversely affect the prognosis [2,3]. Therefore, diagnostic studies establishing the microbial etiology of LRTI are fundamental to provide effective therapy and administration of appropriate antibiotics to the patients [4,5].

Currently, antimicrobial therapy of LRTI is typically initiated on an empirical basis, because of the traditional diagnostic methods including standard culture and antigen detection assay are not able to detect significant proportion of causative pathogens [6,7]. In addition, standard culture and antibiotic susceptibility tests are time-consuming processes, which require at least 24-48 hours [8]. It is known that delay in antibiotic administration is associated with increased in-hospital mortality, especially in severe infections such as pneumonia [9].

Over the last few years, molecular techniques have emerged as the diagnostic tool of choice for respiratory microorganisms, particularly for viruses, fastidious bacteria (*H. influenza*, *S. pneumonia* etc) with difficulty in growing in culture plates, less viable or present in only small number [4,10]. These molecular techniques are also less likely to be affected by the administered empirical or prior antibiotic than standard culture [11,12]. In addition, molecular techniques are able to detect the causative microorganism more quickly than the

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standard culture methods and that may expedite the better-targeted antimicrobial treatment and improve the antibiotic stewardship [11,13].

The aim of our study is to evaluate the utility of a comprehensive molecular diagnostic approach encompassing 7 respiratory bacterial and 15 viral pathogens in tracheal aspirate culture in patients with suspected LRTI during intensive care unit (ICU) stay.

Material and Methods

Study design and setting

This cross-sectional study was performed in accordance with the Strengthening the Reporting of Observational studies in Epidemiology (STROBE) tool [14] and in line with the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki, in a tertiary level training and research hospital with hundred bed capacity. This study was approved by Bozok University Ethical Committee (2018-KAEK-189_2018.01.25_29).

Patients and variables

Patients who were followed up in the ICU with different diagnoses, and suspected of LRTI, were included in the study. Patients who had new or evolving cough, dyspnoea, sputum production, clinical signs of LRTI (rales, wheezing, bronchial breathing, crepitus, or silence), fever ($\geq 38^{\circ}\text{C}$), or a finding on X-ray.

Patients' demographics, medical history, clinical features, laboratory and radiologic findings data were obtained from patient files and electronic medical records. The primary outcomes of this study were the positivity rates of the conventional tracheal aspirate culture and the multiplex PCR of tracheal specimens.

Laboratory procedures

The samples collected from LRTI patients for culture and PCR tests. After using it for culture tests, the rest were stored at -80°C for use in PCR tests. Biosafety rules were followed while collecting samples.

Conventional microbiological investigations (microscopy and culture) were performed from tracheal aspirate specimen of the patients. A biochip array technology assay which provides rapid and broad range of clinically relevant microorganism including 15 respiratory viruses and 7 respiratory bacterial pathogens from endotracheal aspirate specimens was used. The included pathogens were; Influenza A virus, Influenza B virus, Respiratory Syncytial virus A, Human Respiratory Syncytial virus B, Human parainfluenza virus 1, Human parainfluenza virus 2, Human parainfluenza virus 3, Human parainfluenza virus 4, Human coronavirus 229E/NL63, Human coronavirus OC43/HKU1, Human adenovirus A/B/C/D/E, Human rhinovirus A/B/C, Human enterovirus A/B/C, Human bocavirus 1/2/3, Human metapneumovirus, *Legionella pneumophila*, *Chlamydomphila pneumonia*, *Mycoplasma pneumonia*, *Moraxella catarrhalis*, *Streptococcus pneumonia*, *Bordetella pertussis* and *Haemophilus influenza*.

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QIAamp MinElute Virus Spin Kit (QIAGEN, Valencia, CA) was used for RNA/DNA extraction from tracheal aspirate specimens. The Respiratory Multiplex Array II (Randox Biosciences, UK) in combination with the Veriti® (Applied Biosystems, Foster City, CA, USA) rapid thermal cycler, was used. All specimens were analyzed according to the manufacturers' instructions.

The assay is based on a combination of multiplex PCR and biochip array hybridisation. Innovative PCR priming technology permits high discrimination between multiple targets. A unique primer set is designed for each target which will hybridise to a complementary oligo-nucleotide probe spotted on a biochip discrete test region (DTR). This combination of priming and spatially organized biochip array technology enables enhanced specificity of the assay. Analysis can be completed from template DNA and RNA through PCR to data readout in ~6 hours.

Statistical Analysis

Statistical analyses were conducted using SPSS version 20 statistical package program (IBM Corp. in Armonk, NY). Descriptive data are presented as the median with interquartile range (IQR) for numerical variables, and as the frequency with percentage for categorical variables. Tracheal aspirate culture and PCR positivity rates for pathogens with 95% confidence intervals were calculated using Generalized Linear Model with binomial distribution.

Results

During the study period, we evaluated 100 patients for eligibility. After excluding 22 patients due to missing information's, finally, 78 patients were included in the analysis. The median age was 68.5 years, and the males were 60.3%, the women were 39.7% of the study population. Of the patients, 25 had a normal weight, and 52 had a high BMI. More than half of the patients had fever, 28 of them had productive cough, and there were radiologic findings (infiltration, opacity etc) on CXR in 39 patients. Almost all patients had at least one comorbid condition, the most common were hypertension, renal failure, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) and diabetes mellitus (DM). Past medical history revealed that forty-six patients had a history of surgical operation (Table 1).

Table 2 presents clinical and laboratory features of the patients. Twenty-seven patients were admitted to ICU with respiratory failure and 23 with cardiac failure. The median time from hospitalization to ICU admission was 1.0 day, the median time from hospitalization to intubation was 6.0 days, and the median time from ICU admission to intubation was 2.0 days. Twelve patients had need for tracheostomy and the median time between ICU admission and tracheostomy was 13.0 days. The median length of intubation was 8.5 days, the length of mechanical ventilation was 4.0 days, and the median length of admission in the ICU was 12.5 days. The ICU mortality of the study population was 70.5% (55 patients) (Table 2).

Table 3 presents the tracheal aspirate culture results of the patients. *Acinetobacter baumannii* was the most frequent microorganism identified 2 (1.8%) in the tracheal aspirate

cultures, followed by *Escherichia coli* (11.5%), *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (10.3%), and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (5.1%) (Table 3).

Table 4 shows the PCR results of the patients. The most commonly identified pathogens were *Streptococcus pneumoniae* (33.3%), *Haemophilus influenzae* (23.1%), Influenza A virus (12.8%), Human adenovirus (11.5%), *Moraxella catarrhalis* (9.0%), Human coronavirus 229E/NL63 (6.4%), and Human rhinovirus (6.4%), respectively (Table 4).

Table 5 presents the comparison of culture and PCR results. Of 38 culture negative specimens, 30 (78.9%) showed positive PCR results for at least one of the pathogens, furthermore 23 (57.5%) of the culture positive specimens were PCR positive for at least one of the pathogens other than grown in culture (Table 5).

Discussion

Early identification of causative pathogens and administration of appropriate antibiotics in LRTI can decrease the mortality and prevent the overuse of broad-spectrum antibiotics [9]. It is known that traditional diagnostic methods, such as culture of lower respiratory tract specimens and serological examination of blood or urine, are not always sufficient to determine the causative pathogens [4,5]. Therefore, new diagnostic methods targeting to increase the success of detection of causative agents, are one of the investigation fields of current studies [7,15]. In the presented study, we compared to the performance of a multiplex PCR array for common respiratory pathogens. It was found that the rate of identification of causative agents in endotracheal aspirate samples in patients with LRTI by multiplex PCR was 67.9% while it was 51.7% in the culture method.

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Previous studies have demonstrated significant variation in the incidence of bacterial and viral causes of LRTI [3,16]. Quah et al. demonstrated that the most common bacteria isolated was *S. pneumonia* and the most common virus isolated was *Influenza A* [17]. In the presented study, two thirds of the microorganisms detected by PCR, were bacteria species, and the rest were viruses. In addition, we found that *S. pneumonia* and *Influenza A* were the most common bacterial and viral agents, respectively.

In our study, respiratory viruses were detected in approximately two-five (42.3%) (Influenza A virus 12.8%, Human Adenovirus 11.5%, Human coronavirus 229E NL63 6.4%, Human rhinovirus 6.4%, Human parainfluenza virus 1 1.3%, Human parainfluenza virus 3 2.6%, Human parainfluenza virus 41.3%) of the patients, which is in agreement with the literature, it was reported between the 7.7% and 57% range in previous studies [3,5,7,21,22]. This variation in the detection rate of viruses reflects the heterogeneity of patient groups included in the studies and limited availability of test assays [23,24]. Also, influenza viruses were detected in 12.8% of the patients (because it coincides with the seasonal influenza period) and that was comparable with the previous studies, it was reported around 10% in previous studies [5,6,25].

It has been emphasized in the literature that traditional culture tests for detecting causative agents have lower sensitivity and specificity than multiplex PCR methods [4,11]. In addition, the requirement of different culture media for different microorganism is another disadvantage of traditional culture methods [18]. It was reported that PCR methods were more successful for detection of slow and hard growing atypical or fastidious bacteria [19,20]. Gadsby et al. [5], demonstrated that the use of molecular testing approach doubles microorganism's detection in patients with community acquired pneumonia. Similarly,

Aydemir et al. [11], showed that the rate of bacterial identification by molecular method was roughly twice in culture method. In our study, *S. pneumonia* detected by PCR method but not culture, and also only PCR method detected atypical, fastidious or other microorganisms affected with previous antibiotic using. *M. catarrhalis* was detected in 9% of patients, *B. pertussis* and *L. pneumophila* were detected in 1 (1.3%) patient, each. A discordant result for *S. pneumonia* was observed in the presented study. Even though, *S. pneumonia* was observed as the most prevalent organism in multiplex PCR assay, it was not detected in any culture samples. We thought that the probable cause of this condition is due to antibiotic usage prior to sampling. Because the nucleic acid of an organism may persist in vivo, independent of the organism's viability and this affects the results of a multiplex PCR assay [4]. In addition, the colonizing organisms in the upper respiratory tracts such as *S. pneumonia* and detection of these organisms in a multiplex PCR assay leads to a diagnostic dilemma [4]. Molecular methods, which may detect and quantify the microbial load as the culture methods, are more likely to be a directive technique for accurate diagnosis of causative pathogens and appropriate treatment of infection [26].

In our study, 18 (23.1% of patients) specimens of *H. influenza* were observed by multiplex PCR assay but were not found in culture due to the fastidious nature of the *H. influenzae*. Similarly, the diagnosis of *Legionella*, *Bordetella* and *Moraxella* infections have been limited by difficulties in culture methods [19,27,28].

For initiation of the appropriate antibiotic therapy and increasing the treatment success, it is crucial to know the causative agents and their resistance properties in the general population before starting empirical treatment [9]. In our study, we used a multiplex PCR assay detecting only common respiratory bacterial and viral pathogens in patient's samples;

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it did not include detection of any resistance genes. Knowing the antimicrobial resistance profile is very important in terms of determining and applying antimicrobial treatment. However, currently, new multiplex PCR methods have begun to develop for detection of common causative agents and their epidemiological resistance profiles [4,15]. We thought that those new multiplex PCR methods would replace the old ones which only identifies bacterial species but do not include resistance genes.

One limitation of our study was that microscopic evaluation for tracheal aspirate quality is not routinely performed locally in all samples, but only mucopurulent material was tested. Tracheal aspirate, is expectorated from the lower respiratory tract, and always have possibility of oropharyngeal flora contamination. Collecting tracheal aspirate to aid microbial diagnosis was recommended in the pneumonia guidelines [29,30]. Although, alternative lower respiratory tract specimens such as bronchoalveolar lavage or protected brush specimens may be expected to be less at risk for contamination, these methods require semi-invasive procedure and not commonly used in many clinics [4]. Second limitation was that the patients included in the study were highly heterogeneous. Patients, who required admission to ICU, with various causes of respiratory tract infections, including community acquired pneumonia, health-care associated pneumonia and other lower respiratory tract infections were included in the presented study. Another limitation of the study was that we did not evaluate the mix infection. Readers should keep all limitations in mind when interpreting the results of this study.

Conclusion

LRTI is a common cause of admission to the ICUs and it is associated with high morbidity and mortality rates. Our data demonstrate the patterns of bacterial and viral pathogens of LRTI in patients hospitalized in ICU. In conclusion, the multiplex PCR method provides the rapid identification of causative agents, including both bacterial and viral pathogens. We thought that the widespread use of PCR methods, especially including epidemiologically important resistance genes of common bacteria, could compose a cornerstone for antimicrobial stewardship programs in the future. The use of molecular studies, especially in the diagnosis of viral agents, will prevent unnecessary antibiotic use in viral infections and prevent the development of antimicrobial resistance. Therefore, their importance and effectiveness for fighting global antimicrobial resistance threat should be investigated in comprehensive studies.

Declarations

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Conflict of interest

The authors have no conflicts of interest to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.

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Table 1. Demographics and baseline features of the patients

Characteristics (n=78)	
Age (years), median (IQR)	68.5 (59.0-79.5)
Sex (male), n (%)	47 (60.3)
BMI, n (%)	
Underweight	1 (1.3)
Normal weight	25 (32.1)
Overweight	40 (51.3)
Obese	12 (15.4)
Fever, n (%)	44 (56.4)
Productive cough, n (%)	28 (35.9)
Pulmonary infiltration on CXR, n (%)	39 (50.0)
Comorbid condition, n (%)	73 (93.6)
Hypertension	58 (74.4)
Renal failure	33 (42.3)
COPD	18 (23.1)
Diabetes Mellitus	16 (20.5)
CVA	4 (5.1)
Surgical history, n (%)	46 (59.0)

Note: IQR: Interquartile range, BMI: Body mass index, ICU: Intensive care unit, COPD:

Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, CVA: Cerebrovascular accident.

Table 2. Clinical and laboratory features of the patients

Characteristics (n=78)	
Cause of admission to ICU, n (%) ^a	
Respiratory failure	27 (34.6)
Cardiac failure	23 (29.5)
Cardiopulmonary arrest	8 (10.3)
Neurologic dysfunction	1 (1.3)
Other ^b	42 (53.8)
Laboratory findings on admission to ICU, median (IQR)	
Hemoglobin	10.6 (9.4-12.7)
WBC	11750.0 (9150.0-15125.0)
Platelet	184.5 (126.5-251.2)
Urea	71.5 (40.5-119.0)
Creatinine	1.3 (0.9-2.0)
CRP	100.1 (32.3-162.3)
Time-to-ICU ^c (days), median (IQR)	1.0 (0.0-8.2)
Time-to-intubation ^d (days), median (IQR)	6.0 (1.0-19.0)
Time from ICU to intubation ^e (days), median (IQR)	2.0 (0.0-6.2)
Need for tracheostomy, n (%)	12 (15.4)
Time-to-tracheostomy ^f (n=12) (days), median (IQR)	13.0 (10.0-21.5)
Length of intubation (days), median (IQR)	8.5 (2.0-25.5)
Length of mechanical ventilation (days), median (IQR)	4.0 (2.0-20.5)

Length of stay in ICU (days), median (IQR)	12.5 (5.7-33.0)
ICU mortality, n (%)	55 (70.5)

Note: ICU: Intensive care unit, IQR: Interquartile range.

a Some patients were admitted for more than one cause.

b Other causes include; malignancies, hepatic failure, renal failure, postoperative causes.

c Time elapsed from hospitalization to ICU admission.

d Time elapsed from hospitalization to intubationd (days), median (IQR)

e Time elapsed from ICU to intubatione (days), median (IQR)

f Time elapsed from ICU to tracheostomy performingf (days), median (IQR)

Table 3. *Tracheal aspirate culture results of the patients*

Microbiological agent (n=78)	Positivity	
	Frequency	Percentage (95% CI)
Acinetobacter baumannii	17	21.8 (12.6 – 31.0)
Escherichia coli	9	11.5 (4.4 – 18.6)
Klebsiella pneumoniae	8	10.3 (3.5 – 17.0)
Pseudomonas aeruginosa	4	5.1 (0.2 – 10.0)
Staphylococcus aureus	3	3.8 (-0.4 – 8.1)
Stenotrophomonas maltophilia	3	3.8 (-0.4 – 8.1)
Enterobacter cloacae	1	1.3 (-1.2 – 3.8)
Klebsiella oxytoca	1	1.3 (-1.2 – 3.8)

Table 4. *Tracheal aspirate PCR results of the patients*

Microbiological agent (n=78)	Positivity	
	Frequency	Percentage (95% CI)
Streptococcus pneumoniae	26	33.3 (22.9 – 43.8)
Haemophilus influenzae	18	23.1 (13.7 – 32.4)
Influenza A virus	10	12.8 (5.4 – 20.2)
Human adenovirus	9	11.5 (4.4 – 18.6)
Moraxella catarrhalis	7	9.0 (2.6 – 15.3)
Human coronavirus 229E NL63	5	6.4 (1.0 – 11.8)
Human rhinovirus	5	6.4 (1.0 – 11.8)
Bordetella pertussis	1	1.3 (-1.2 – 3.8)
Legionella pneumophila	1	1.3 (-1.2 – 3.8)
Human parainfluenza virus 1	1	1.3 (-1.2 – 3.8)
Human parainfluenza virus 3	2	2.6 (-0.9 – 6.1)
Human parainfluenza virus 4	1	1.3 (-1.2 – 3.8)

Note: Influenza B, Human coronavirus OC43/HKUI, Human enterovirus, Human metapneumovirus, Human parainfluenza virus 2, Human respiratory syncytial virus A and B, Chlamydomphila pneumonia, Mycoplasma pneumonia weren't detected in the study although they were included in the kit.

Table 5. Comparison of culture and PCR for positive and negative cases

		PCR				Total	
		Negative		Positive		n	%
		n	%	n	%		
Tracheal	Negative	8	21.1	30	78.9	38	100.0
aspirate culture	Positive	17	42.5	23	57.5	40	100.0
Total		25	32.1	53	67.9	78	100.0

Prevalence of pathogens in intensive care unit patients with lower respiratory tract infections: Culture with/without Polymerase Chain Reaction?

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